

1 **Genes whose mutation or natural variation confers susceptibility to autism are differentially**
2 **expressed in the autistic brain.**

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7 Traditional approaches have utilized genomic technology and genetic screening in populations to identify
8 statistical associations between the autistic disease phenotype and variation or mutation of a gene (SNP).
9 We demonstrate here that using whole transcriptome technology that variants identified as causative or
10 associated genetic factors in ASD are differentially expressed genes in the brains of humans with ASD.
11 This includes members of the axon guidance family whose neurodevelopmental function appears central
12 to the etiology of autism. Loss or gain of function can be measured as differences in expression level and
13 we presume its phenotypic consequence likely mirrors that which occurs by variation resulting from
14 germline or de novo mutation.
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